

DEVELOPMENT OF THE ROVER PERMITTIVITY SENSOR SUITE FOR THE RASHID-3 MISSION.

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Introduction: Quantifying and mapping water ice occurrences on the Moon is among the top priorities of future lunar missions [1]. To this end, we are developing the Rover Permittivity Sensor (RPS) suite as a contribution of the European Space Agency to the upcoming Rashid-3 rover mission of the United Arab Emirates. The suite includes two sensing electrodes on a wheel of the rover to measure the dielectric permittivity of the lunar soil along the rover's traverse. Additionally, a temperature sensor embedded in one of the electrodes and an infrared temperature sensor mounted on the rover body will measure the soil surface temperature.

The technology employed for permittivity measurement is a development partially based on early prototype developments at ESA [2], and a subsequent flight-model implementation for the P-Sensor of the PROSPECT instrument package [3,4]. The electrical permittivity can be used to infer the soil porosity and ice content, as the relative (static) permittivity of vacuum, dry regolith, and water ice differ significantly [5,6,7]. Additionally, the polarisation of the water molecule can be detected by analysing signal response in the frequency domain [3,8]. As the signal response is highly temperature-dependent, the RPS suite also features contact-based temperature measurements of the regolith surface via a resistive temperature sensor integrated into one of the electrodes, located close to the material exposed to the electrode current. This will be correlated with the contactless surface-temperature measurement by the infrared temperature sensing unit. Measurements of RPS will be conducted at multiple stops during the traverse, when the rover is at rest. The depth to which the electrode measurements can resolve a subsurface ice layer is ~30 mm and ~60 mm, respectively, providing a simple means of depth resolution.

In addition to permittivity and temperature measurements, RPS can detect regolith surface charge as the rover moves. When one of the electrodes rotates towards the surface, a charge is induced in the electrode, and the resulting current is measured.

RPS Design: The entire sensor suite (Figure 1) comprises backend electronics housed in the rover body, a slip ring to feed electrical signals to the rotating wheel, two wheel-mounted electrodes, and an infrared temperature sensing unit.

The electronics include sections for power conditioning, excitation signal generation, electrode current measurement, and temperature and infrared sensor data readout. Telemetry is transmitted via the rover electronics, without requiring digital processing on the RPS side. The electrode signal is a square wave with a variable base frequency ranging from 0.0125 Hz to 1.6 Hz to maximise the detection range across different ice quantities and soil temperatures.

The slip ring is part of the wheel axis and provides a shielded connection of the sensitive electrode measurement signal between the electrodes and the electronics. It was specifically designed for the electrical signal requirements of RPS and to accommodate the mass and volume constraints of the rover wheel. Due to its novelty and the corresponding technology readiness level, it requires a tailored qualification programme, which is currently being prepared.

The rectangular sensing electrodes are mounted with an appropriate angular spacing to one of the front rover wheels, so that they come into contact with the undisturbed regolith once every wheel revolution. An isolating cap shields the sensor electrode, protecting the electronics from electrostatic discharge and the electrode itself from mechanical damage.

The infrared temperature measurement unit is mounted at the front of the rover, with its field of view aligned with the rover's path, to determine the surface temperature of undisturbed regolith before a permittivity measurement is conducted.

Development Status: RPS has completed its prototyping phase and recently concluded the Preliminary Design Review. Unit-level environmental tests have been performed, including vibration testing of the slip ring and electrodes, and thermal-vacuum testing of the electrodes (Figure 2).

Figure 1: Early prototype of RPS, including the electronics (left), slip ring (centre), and two electrodes mounted on a rover wheel mockup (right).

Figure 2: RPS slip ring and electrode vibration testing

To continue de-risking the design, multiple specific test facilities are currently being set up to test the following aspects of the hardware elements:

Slip ring dust testing. The fine fraction of lunar dust is expected to pose a major challenge for all moving parts of the sensor suite, particularly for the slip ring inside the open rover wheel. Dust may be deposited during the spacecraft landing and the rover traverse. The main concern is that dust will enter the slip ring and interact with its electrical tracks and contacts, leading to increased wear and friction torque. As no standardised environmental test for this scenario exists, a dedicated test setup has been developed to enable life testing in a combined dusty and vacuum environment using regolith simulants. It aims to demonstrate the functionality of the slip ring under varying dust loads for a duration of four times the expected lifetime on the Moon.

Electrode wear testing. The abrasiveness of lunar regolith poses a potential hazard to the mechanical robustness of the electrodes mounted on the outer circumference of the rover wheel. Although wheel revolutions are relatively slow and the risk of wheel slip might be low, the extreme and highly variable thermal environment might increase the risk of mechanical wear of the electrode surface. As no standard environmental test for this scenario exists, another dedicated test setup has been developed for this purpose. It comprises a turntable platform on which a wheel mock-up can continuously be rolled. The turntable surface is covered with regolith simulant, while the wheel is continuously cooled using liquid nitrogen. The setup allows for testing comparable materials, contact conditions, motion types, mechanical loads, and temperatures.

Integrated dusty thermal vacuum test. Following testing of the individual units of RPS, an integrated test is planned to verify the functionality and performance of the entire sensor suite. A wheel mock-up will be installed on a movable gantry within a dust-tolerant thermal-vacuum chamber. Here, all units of the sensor suite can be mounted in a flight-like configuration and be life-tested in a vacuum under variable thermal conditions and with realistic dust interaction. The setup currently under construction also features gravity off-loading to test realistic load cases.

References: [1] Reiss, P. (2024), *PNAS*, 121(52). [2] Trautner, R. et al., *37th ESLAB Symposium*, 193–196, 2004. [3] Trautner R. et al. (2024), *Front. Space Tech.*, 5:1331828. [4] Trautner, R. et al. (2021), *Meas. Sci. and Tech.*, 32. [5] Uematsu, M. and Franck, E.U. (1980), *J. of Phys. and Chem. Ref. Data*, 9.4, 1291–1306. [6] Chung, D.H. et al. (1972) *Proc. of the Lunar Sci. Conf.*, 3, 3161. [7] Gscheidle, C. et al. (2024) *Front. in Space Technol.*, 4:1303180. [8] Nurge, M.A. (2012) *Planet. Space Sci.*